

SUCCESSFUL TREATMENT FOR RECURRENT NASAL POLYPS**Bharath Raja**

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Nasal polyps are the benign noncancerous outgrowth in the cavities found in the nasal sinuses. They are not dangerous in the starting stage, but it grows along with ourself and block the nose in the end making a favorable environment for the microbes leading to recurrent infections like chronic sinusitis. And also field studies done in Korea shows that nearly 25% of the patients who got nasal polyps with an old age of nearly 50-60 age were more prone to get head and neck cancer, but the direct connection between them are yet to be discovered. So, it is better to treat nasal polyps without any recurrence can be done by Advanced Functional Endoscopic Sinus Surgery [FESS] and post- surgical implant named SINUVA, a mometasone furoate shows better prognosis and less recurrence.

Purpose of work:

It is important to study about the new and better technique of treatment of nasal polyps which has a highly recurrence rate and to avoid further complications of asthma exacerbation, repeated infection of nasal cavity and severe sleep apnea which decrease the quality of life.

Material and methods:

Research articles and other databases which shows the high successful rate of the treatment methods for the recurrent polyps have been used to provide a keen review.

Results of the study:

Scientific researches and many surgical trials done among the patients have shown the low recurrence rate with the help of Advanced Functional Endoscopic Sinus Surgery [FESS] and with a post surgically implanted mometasone. FESS is a

minimally invasive technique which is done with the help of endoscopes and 3-D imaging guidance under general anesthesia. The preoperational measures like advising quit smoking, avoiding the blood thinners and using nasal decongestant before surgery to get a better view. Then the endoscopes are being guided inside the nasal cavity with the help of cameras clearing the nasal cavity by drainage of mucus and clearing the other blockage. Based on the need and type of severity, this surgery is divided with methods like balloon sinuplasty which dilates the pathway near the polyp and polypectomy is done after that by preserving middle turbinate which is resected by half in those old surgeries involving polypectomy in those who have the obstructed field to access the sinuses. Thereby, avoiding complications like anosmia and preserving the dynamic airflow. And a Modified Lothrop Procedure can be done for mainly recurrent severe frontal sinus polyps by removing the frontal nasal floor and superior nasal septum after bilateral ethmoidectomy to get a good air flow inside the sinus, thereby decreasing the recurrent infection and recurrence of nasal polyps. After successfully resecting the nasal polyps by those above methods, post operational implantation of mometasone which is a bioabsorbable steroid eluting device placed mainly in the ethmoid sinus to reduce the inflammation caused by the surgery and to suppress the regrowth of nasal polyps.

Conclusion:

Hereby, the use of Functional Endoscopic Sinus Surgery [FESS] followed by post operational implant of mometasone providing the synergistic effect of minimizing the progression of regrowth of recurrent and persistent nasal polyps providing a better successful rate while other medications shows failure and recurrence of nasal polyps.

Reference:

- 1.) <https://www.nhs.uk/conditions/nasal-polyps/>
- 2.) <https://my.clevelandclinic.org/health/diseases/15250-nasal-polyps>

3.)<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/36848271/>

4.)<https://www.mdpi.com/2673-351X/5/1/4>

5.)<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC4961632/>

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